

Study of Microalbuminuria as a Marker of Target Organ Damage in Cases of Essential Hypertension**A. Raghu Rama Reddy¹, Cheeti Upendar Rao²**¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, Prathima Institute of Medical Sciences, Naganoor, Karimnagar, Telangana State.²Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Prathima Institute of Medical Sciences, Naganoor, Karimnagar, Telangana State.

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Abstract:**Background:** Urinary albumin excretion has been strongly associated with cardiovascular events in hypertensive patients. This study evaluated the prevalence of microalbuminuria in patients with essential hypertension and its relationship with target organ damage, as previous research has not extensively explored the correlation between microalbuminuria and target organ damage beyond cardiovascular events.**Methods:** sixty cases of essential hypertension were enrolled sequentially. The prevalence of urinary albumin excretion and its correlation with target organ damage (left ventricular hypertrophy, retinopathy, and stroke) were analyzed. Microalbuminuria was examined using the immunoturbidimetric method using Erba Chem 5 Plus V2 Semiautomated Analyzer.**Results:** Our data show a higher prevalence of hypertension in the 41-50 age group, predominantly affecting males. Microalbuminuria, an early indicator of kidney damage, was significantly linked to hypertension, especially in patients with a longer duration of the disease and those with inadequate medication control. The result of this study shows a strong association between essential hypertension and its complications. Additionally, patients with microalbuminuria were more likely to develop target organ damage, including stroke, retinopathy, and left ventricular hypertrophy.**Conclusion:** Microalbuminuria in hypertensive patients could be a useful predictor for evaluating target organ damage. Managing preventable risk factors, such as maintaining regular hypertension treatment, controlling weight, and keeping lipid levels normal, may help reduce the occurrence of microalbuminuria. Prompt screening for microalbuminuria in individuals with known hypertension, followed by adequate treatment, could potentially decrease the incidence of chronic kidney disease and cardiovascular disease.**Keywords:** Microalbuminuria, Essential Hypertension, Target Organ Damage.

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Introduction

Hypertension is a major global health issue, responsible for killing and disabling a large number of patients through its various complications. Hypertension affects approximately 1 billion people worldwide [1]. The relationship between blood pressure and the risk of coronary vascular disease is continuous, consistent, and independent of other risk factors [1]. Adequate hypertension control remains elusive, primarily due to the asymptomatic nature of the disease for the first 15-20 years, even as it progressively damages the cardiovascular system. Coronary heart disease is the leading cause of mortality and morbidity, and the significance of hypertension as a risk factor for coronary heart disease is well established [2].

Benign arteriolar nephrosclerosis in hypertensive patients (BP over 140/90 mmHg) over an extended period may manifest as mild to moderate elevation

of serum creatinine, microscopic hematuria, and/or microalbuminuria [3]. The association between microalbuminuria and hypertension was described by Parving et al. in 1974 [3, 4]. Microalbuminuria has a major impact on cardiovascular risk [3]. In recent years, microalbuminuria has become a prognostic marker for cardiovascular disorders [5]. In essential hypertension, increased trans glomerular passage of albumin may result from mechanisms such as hyperfiltration [6], glomerular basal membrane abnormalities, endothelial dysfunction, and nephrosclerosis [3]. Microalbuminuria, which represents an albumin excretion rate (AER) of 30-300 mg/24 hours, is defined as elevated urinary albumin excretion below the level of clinical albuminuria, undetectable by Albustix and detectable only by special methods [3]. Microalbuminuria's prognostic

role extends to the early detection and intervention in patients with hypertensive nephropathy. Therefore, it is crucial to detect nephropathy as early as possible to take proper precautions and initiate appropriate management [3]. Several epidemiological studies have shown that proteinuria and microalbuminuria are independent predictors of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality in patients with essential hypertension. The most recent Joint National Commission on Hypertension (JNC VII) report includes microalbuminuria as evidence of target organ damage, indicating the need for more aggressive blood pressure control [7]. This study aimed to detect microalbuminuria in Albustix-negative hypertensive patients quantitatively using the immunoturbidimetric method. It also sought to evaluate the prevalence of microalbuminuria in patients with essential hypertension and its relationship to the severity of hypertension, renal function, and its association with coronary artery disease and target organ damage.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was done in the Department of General Medicine, Prathima Institute of Medical Sciences, Naganoor, Karimnagar. Institutional Ethical approval was obtained for the study. Written consent was obtained from all the participants of the study after explaining the nature of the study in the vernacular language.

Inclusion Criteria

1. On treatment of Essential Hypertension
2. Aged 20 and above
3. Males and Females
4. Visiting OPD of General Medicine of our Hospital
5. Voluntarily willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Diabetes mellitus with urine sugar-positive
2. Neoplastic diseases,
3. Urinary tract infections
4. Benign Prostatic hyperplasia
5. Renal calculi

A total of 60 primary hypertensive, non-diabetic patients and 30 healthy normotensive, non-diabetic controls were included in this study. After obtaining informed consent, the name, age, sex,

occupation, and disease duration of each participant were recorded. Detailed histories of various symptoms and clinical examinations were noted. Blood pressure was measured using standard guidelines. Blood and early morning urine samples were collected for the investigations. The morning urine sample without centrifugation from each subject was initially evaluated using a standard dipstick test. The Micral-Test[®] strip Roche Diagnostics was based on an immuno-logical test principle using gold-labeled monoclonal antibodies with a chromogenic color indicator enabling confidence in results. Microalbuminuria is the term used when albumin levels in the urine are 20-200 mg/L [8]. A well-mixed fresh urine sample was centrifuged, and the sediment was examined under a microscope to rule out urinary tract infections or other renal or urinary tract abnormalities. Urine creatinine concentrations <0.04 gm/dl and >0.3 gm/dl were excluded to avoid the effect of muscle mass and age on the calculation of the albumin/creatinine ratio (ACR), as differences in muscle mass and age affect the predictive performance of the ACR. Microalbuminuria was examined using the immunoturbidimetric method using Erba Chem 5 Plus V2 Semiautomated Analyzer. Fasting blood sugar, Blood urea, and Serum creatinine were performed in Erba Chem 5 Plus V2 Semiautomated Analyzer.

Statistical analysis: All the available data was refined and uploaded to an MS Excel spreadsheet and analyzed by SPSS version 21 in Windows format. The continuous variables were denoted as mean, standard deviation, and percentages. The categorical variables were analyzed by chi-square test for p values. The values of p less than 0.05 were considered as significant.

Results

A total of 60 cases were included in the study during the period of the study. Out of these 42 cases were males and 18 were females. The male-to-female ratio was 7:3. The table describes the distribution of cases of essential hypertension included in the study, categorized by age group and gender. Age group 41-50 has the highest number of cases (22), followed by 41-60 (16) and 31- 40 (8). The percentage of cases is highest in the 41-50 age group (36.7%), followed by 51-60 (26.7%) and 31-40 (13.3%).

Table 1: Showing the distribution of cases of essential hypertension included in the study

Age group	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
20 – 30	2	0	2	3.3
31 – 40	6	2	8	13.3
41 – 50	16	6	22	36.7
51 – 60	10	6	16	26.7
61 – 70	8	4	12	20.0
Total	42	18	60	100

Table 2 shows the association between essential hypertension and several risk factors for microalbuminuria. *Gender*: Males were more likely to have microalbuminuria than females ($p = 0.021$). *Obesity*: Obese patients were more likely to have microalbuminuria than non-obese patients ($p = 0.050$). *Blood pressure*: Patients with higher blood pressure were more likely to have microalbuminuria ($p = 0.013$). *Dyslipidemia*:

Patients with dyslipidemia were more likely to have microalbuminuria ($p = 0.002$). These findings suggest that managing these risk factors is important for reducing the risk of microalbuminuria in patients with essential hypertension. This table shows that there is a statistically significant association between all of the listed risk factors and microalbuminuria.

Table 2: Cases of Essential hypertension and risk Factors associated with microalbuminuria

Variable		Total	Microalbumin urea (Positive)	Microalbumin urea (Negative)	P value
Gender	Male	42	25	17	0.021*
	Female	18	9	9	
Obesity	Present	38	22	16	0.05*
	Absent	22	12	10	
Blood pressure (mmHg)	<140/90	10	6	4	0.013*
	140-160/90-100	38	20	18	
	>160/100	12	8	4	
Dyslipidemia	Present	40	26	14	0.002*
	Absent	20	8	12	

*Significant

Table 3 depicts the relationship between microalbuminuria and two factors: duration of hypertension and use of antihypertensive medications. *Duration of Hypertension*: There is a statistically significant association between the duration of hypertension and the presence of microalbuminuria (p -value = 0.022). As the duration of hypertension increases, the prevalence of microalbuminuria also increases. *Antihypertensive Medications*: Regular use of

antihypertensive medications is associated with a lower prevalence of microalbuminuria compared to those with no or irregular medication use (p -value = 0.004). This indicates that consistent treatment of hypertension can help reduce the risk of developing microalbuminuria. The results suggest that both the duration of hypertension and the adherence to antihypertensive medication regimens are important factors in the development of microalbuminuria. These findings emphasize the importance of early detection and treatment of hypertension to prevent kidney damage.

Table 3: Association of microalbuminuria with duration of hypertension and medications

		Frequency of cases	Microalbuminuria present	P value
Duration of hypertension	1 – 3 years	12 (21.7%)	5 (41.7%)	0.022*
	3 – 5 years	26 (43.3%)	16 (61.5%)	
	> 5 years	14 (23.3%)	10 (71.4%)	
	Unknown	8 (13.3%)	45 (0.0%)	
Antihypertensive medications	No	16 (26.7)	9 (56.2%)	0.004*
	Regular	34 (56.7)	12 (35.3%)	
	Irregular	10 (16.7)	7 (70.0%)	

* Significant

Table 4 shows the relationship between microalbuminuria and various target organ damages associated with hypertension, including stroke, retinopathy, and left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH). There is a statistically significant association between microalbuminuria and all three target organ damages: stroke, retinopathy, and left ventricular hypertrophy. A high proportion of patients with stroke (87.5%), retinopathy (76.5%), and LVH (83.3%) also had microalbuminuria. The

results suggest that microalbuminuria is a significant marker for the presence of target organ damage in patients with hypertension. Patients with microalbuminuria are at a substantially higher risk of developing complications such as stroke, retinopathy, and heart problems. These findings underscore the importance of early detection and management of microalbuminuria to prevent or delay the progression of target organ damage.

Table 4: Association of target organ damage with presence of microalbuminuria

Target organ damage	Frequency	Microalbuminuria	P value
Stroke	8 (13.3%)	7 (87.5%)	0.002
Retinopathy	17 (28.3%)	13 (76.5%)	0.031
Left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH)	12 (20.0%)	10 (83.3%)	0.001

Discussion

The important findings of the current study indicate a strong association between essential hypertension and its complications. Our data reveals a higher prevalence of hypertension in the 41-50 age group, with a male predominance. Microalbuminuria, a marker for early kidney damage, was significantly linked to hypertension, particularly in patients with longer disease duration and those without adequate medication control. Moreover, patients with microalbuminuria exhibited a higher likelihood of developing target organ damage, including stroke, retinopathy, and left ventricular hypertrophy.

Microalbuminuria is commonly observed in patients with essential hypertension and is a well-established predictor of increased risk for cardiovascular and possibly renal dysfunction, as well as subsequent mortality. In this study, we found microalbuminuria (MA) was found in 34 (56.7%) participants, a prevalence higher than that reported in previous similar studies (6.7%-40.0%) [9-13]. This higher prevalence could be partly attributed to the comparatively higher blood pressure levels among participants in this study and the fact that most patients were not compliant with treatment.

Microalbuminuria has increasingly been recognized as a marker of cardiovascular risk in diabetic individuals [14, 15]. Its significance in cases of essential hypertension is also becoming clearer with each study. MA has been associated with factors such as increasing age, longer duration, and greater severity of hypertension, obesity, and dyslipidemia; the findings in this study align with existing evidence [16-18]. Left ventricular hypertrophy (94.28%) and stroke (92.3%) were significantly more common in those with MA, as were progressive retinopathy changes (72.54%). Retinopathy, LVH, stroke, and dyslipidemia remained independently associated with MA even after multivariate analysis. This suggests that hypertensive patients with MA have a significantly higher risk of developing both macrovascular and microvascular complications compared to those without MA. Pontremoli et al. [19] reported significant correlations between MA and target organ damage (TOD), including major ECG abnormalities and vascular retinal changes, while Hitha et al. [20] observed a similar correlation between the presence of MA and a higher incidence of stroke and retinopathy, further supporting these observations. MA is considered the renal

manifestation of generalized increased endothelial dysfunction as part of the disease process, leading to the hypothesis that a correlation exists between cardiovascular risk factors and the progression from early to advanced renal damage [21].

Conclusion

Microalbuminuria in hypertensive patients could be a useful predictor for evaluating target organ damage. Managing preventable risk factors, such as maintaining regular hypertension treatment, controlling weight, and keeping lipid levels normal, may help reduce the occurrence of microalbuminuria. Prompt screening for microalbuminuria in individuals with known hypertension, followed by adequate treatment, could potentially decrease the incidence of chronic kidney disease and cardiovascular disease.

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